

Parametric study of the small scale Linear Fresnel Reflector

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Abstract

This paper addresses the influence of the transversal and longitudinal parameters in the performance of a small scale linear Fresnel reflector (SSLFR) without longitudinal movement. The main purpose of this study is to show the influence of the design parameters (receiver height, mirror length, and mirror width) on the energy absorbed by the absorber tube. In addition, the influence of these parameters on the shading of the absorber tube is also analysed. Different configurations are analysed regarding the longitudinal angle that the mirrors and the absorber tube form with the horizontal plane. Each of these configurations is analysed considering the optimal length and longitudinal position of the absorber tube. Numerical simulations show the influence of mirror width, mirror length, and receiver height on the energy absorbed. The simulations allow us to analyze the monthly variation of this influence throughout the year, considering also the effect of the latitude. A sensitivity analysis is also carried out in order to evaluate the importance of the parameters.

Keywords: Linear Fresnel Reflector, Parametric study, Sensitivity analysis

1. Introduction

Linear Fresnel Reflectors (LFRs) are becoming an option to generate electricity from solar radiation, although almost all recent Solar Thermal Power Plants are parabolic trough plants. Apart from prototypes, there are several commercial LFR plants for power generation: Kimberlina Solar

14 Thermal Power Plant (see NREL, 2017) (5 MW) in California, (USA); Liddell
15 Power Station’s solar boiler (9.3 MW) in Australia; Puerto Errado 2 (30 MW)
16 in Spain; and Dhursar (125 MW) in India. LFR plants are built using two
17 different configurations (see Abbas et al. 2013 and Montes et al. 2014): the
18 central LFR, where the receiver is in the centre of the mirror array; and
19 the compact linear Fresnel collector (CLFC) (Mills et al. 2000), where there
20 is a receiver at each side of the mirror array so that consecutive mirrors
21 point to a different receiver. The main advantage of the CLFC configuration
22 against the central LFR is that blocking optical losses are smaller, since
23 consecutive mirrors point to a different receiver depending on the incidence
24 angle. Furthermore, several authors have studied the different characteristics
25 of both configurations (see, for example, Abbas et al. 2012, Lin et al. 2013,
26 Natarajan et al. 2012, or Pino et al. 2013), namely: receiver design (multiple
27 tube receiver or single-tube receiver), mirror construction (curved or flat),
28 and secondary concentrator design (with or without secondary concentrator).
29 Particularly, Kimberlina is a CLFC plant, with a multi-tube receiver and
30 without a secondary concentrator; Liddell and Dhursar are CLFC plants,
31 whereas Puerto Errado is a LFR plant, with a single-tube absorber and with
32 a secondary concentrator.

33 LFR technology can be used in other applications, besides electricity
34 generation, as in industrial processes and in the building sector. For example,
35 these collectors can be used in domestic water heating (Sultana et al. 2012
36 and 2015), in an absorption air cooled Solar-GAX cycle (Velazquez et al.
37 2010), or to provide heating/cooling for buildings (Bermejo et al. 2010).
38 These applications are not negligible, since in the European Union (EU)
39 the building sector is one of the highest energy consumers, in particular it
40 represents more than 40% of the final energy consumption (see EU, 2010). In
41 order to improve energy efficiency, the EU (EU 2009) has adopted a series of
42 directives to promote the use of energy from renewable sources in buildings.

43 Numerous authors have made parametric studies of this technology for
44 electricity generation (see, for example, Boito et al. 2016, Abbas et al. 2015,
45 Nixon et al. 2012, or Abbas et al. 2012b), although the longitudinal design
46 has been overlooked in most of these studies. In contrast, there are only a few
47 parametric studies of LFRs in other applications (see Barbón et al. (2016)
48 and Barbón et al. (2016b)). In large scale LFRs the study of the longitudinal
49 behaviour is not usually performed for two reasons: the absorber size does
50 not permit any configuration allowing the modification of its position, and
51 the influence of the longitudinal position can be considered irrelevant in %

52 terms with respect to the total length of the absorber. However, in small
53 scale LFRs (SSLFRs) this is a fundamental study. Another parameter that
54 affects the study of SSLFRs is the area available for installation. In large scale
55 LFRs, the available area is not a critical parameter. In contrast, the mirror
56 field area (A_{fw}) is the starting parameter for the design of a SSLFR. As
57 already mentioned, these SSLFRs can be used in domestic water heating, or
58 to provide heating/cooling for buildings. Therefore, roofs are a logical location
59 for the SSLFR. The installation on building roofs reduces the risk of shading
60 by adjacent buildings, vegetation, or other sources of shadow. However,
61 the roofs of the urban buildings are generally not designed or built to host
62 renewable energy systems. Available roof area has in fact been identified as
63 a main limiting factor in achieving zero energy buildings, especially for taller
64 buildings.

65 The potential number of SSLFRs to be installed on a roof strongly de-
66 pends on the mirror field area. And, as we will see in section 2, this parameter
67 can be expressed in terms of the mirror length, receiver height, and mirror
68 width. Therefore, one of the objectives of this study is to analyze the in-
69 fluence of the variation of these parameters, in a reasonable range, on the
70 energy absorbed by the absorber tube, and, as a consequence, on the poten-
71 tial energy that can be obtained in a particular roof. Another objective is
72 to analyze the influence of these parameters on the shading of the absorber
73 tube on the mirror field area.

74 The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the main angular
75 relationships that will be used throughout the paper, the parameters used
76 in the transversal study, the parameters used in the longitudinal study, and
77 the equation used to determine the power absorbed by the absorber tube.
78 In Section 3 (critical parameters), the parameters used in the comparative
79 analysis are presented. In addition, an evaluation of the shading effect of the
80 absorber tube is carried out. Numerical simulations and sensitivity analysis
81 are presented in Section 4 for different configurations of the LFR. Finally,
82 Section 5 summarizes the main contributions and conclusions of the paper.

Nomenclature

A	Longitudinal component of the reflected radiation	M_{fw}	Mirror Field Width (m)
A_{effi}	Effective area of the absorber tube (m^2)	n	Number of mirrors at each side of the central mirror
A_{fw}	Mirror Field Area (m^2)	Q	Total power absorbed (W)
B_i	Transversal component of the reflected radiation for i -th mirror ($0 \preceq i \preceq n$)	S_t	Transversal shading of the absorber tube (m)
CL_g	Cleanliness factor of the glass	W	Width of the mirrors (m)
CL_m	Cleanliness factor of the mirror	W_{ai}	Width illuminated on the absorber by the i -th by mirror (m)
D	Diameter of the absorber tube (m)	α	Absorptivity of the absorber tube
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiance (W/m^2)	α_i	Angle between the vertical at the focal point and the line connecting the center point of each mirror to the focal point ($^\circ$)
d	Separation between two consecutive mirrors (m)	α_S	Height angle of the Sun ($^\circ$)
f	Height of the receiver (m)	β_a	Angle between the absorber tube and the horizontal plane ($^\circ$)
IAF	Incidence angle modifier	β_i	Tilt of i -th mirror ($^\circ$)
L_{abs}	Length of the single absorber tube (m)	β_M	Angle between the mirror axis and the horizontal plane ($^\circ$)
L_{abs}^l	Left length of the single absorber tube (m)	γ_S	Azimuth of the sun ($^\circ$)
L_{abs}^r	Right length of the single absorber tube (m)	η_{opt}	Optical efficiency (%)
l_{abs}	Total illuminated length of the single absorber tube (m)	θ_i	Angle between the normal to the mirror and the angle of incidence of the sun ($^\circ$)
L_{ai}	Length of the circumference illuminated on the absorber by the i -th mirror (m)	θ_L	Lateral incidence angle ($^\circ$)
L_i	Position of i -th mirror ($0 \preceq i \preceq n$) (m)	θ_l	Longitudinal incidence angle ($^\circ$)
L_i^l	L_i of the left side (m)	θ_t	Transversal incidence angle ($^\circ$)
L_i^r	L_i of the right side (m)	θ_z	Zenith angle of the Sun ($^\circ$)
L_M	Length of the mirrors (m)	λ	Latitude angle ($^\circ$)
L_{ts}	Position of transversal shading of the absorber tube (m)	μ	Angle between the reflected ray and the normal to the NS axis ($^\circ$)
l_{abs}^l	Left illuminated length of the single absorber tube (m)	ρ	Reflectivity of the primary mirrors
l_{abs}^r	Right illuminated length of the single absorber tube (m)	τ	Transmissivity of the glass

83 **2. Problem statement and definitions**

84 The SSLFR, as shown in Fig. 1.a, is composed of two main blocks: the
 85 primary reflector system and the secondary reflector system. The primary
 86 reflector system is composed of a fixed frame with rows of mirrors. The
 87 secondary reflector system consists of an absorber tube and an absorber
 88 cavity. The secondary reflector system is located at a certain height from
 89 the primary reflector system. Each row of mirrors tracks the sun on one
 90 axis (East-West axis tracking). The assumptions made in this study are as
 91 follows:

- 92 (i) The mirrors are flat and specularly reflecting.
- 93 (ii) The rows of mirrors are perfectly tracked so as to follow the apparent
 94 movement of the Sun.
- 95 (iii) The pivoting point of each mirror coincides with the central point of
 96 the mirror; hence, it is always focused on the central point of the absorber
 97 tube.
- 98 (iv) An appropriate distance (shift) must be kept between two consecutive
 99 mirrors so that a mirror does not shade its adjacent mirror element.
- 100 (v) A single absorber tube is used.
- 101 (vi) The design of the absorber tube and the absorber cavity will not be
 102 taken into consideration.

Fig. 1 The SSLFR.

103 *2.1. Angular relationships*

104 Considering a SSLFR aligned horizontally and aligned in a North-South
 105 orientation, the angle of incidence of solar radiation will be calculated in two

106 projection planes: the transversal incidence angle (θ_t) and the longitudinal
 107 incidence angle (θ_l), (see Theunissen et al. 1985). The transversal incidence
 108 angle (θ_t) is defined as the angle between the vertical and the projection of
 109 the sun vector on the East-West plane (the plane orthogonal to the absorber
 110 tube), and the longitudinal incidence angle (θ_l) is defined as the angle be-
 111 tween the vertical and the projection of the sun vector on the North-South
 112 plane.

113 2.2. Parameters used in the transversal study

114 As shown in Barbon et al. (2016), each mirror can be characterized by
 115 two parameters: position with respect to the central mirror (L_i), and tilt
 116 (β_i). The position (L_i) depends on the mirror width (W) and the mirror
 117 separation (d). The tilt (β_i) depends on the receiver height (f), the diameter
 118 of the absorber tube (D), and the transversal incidence angle (θ_t). If n is
 119 the number of mirrors at each side of the central mirror, the total number of
 120 mirrors of the SSLFR is $2n + 1$.

121 The illuminated width on the absorber tube by the i -th mirror (W_{ai}) is
 122 given by:

$$W_{ai} = W [\cos \beta_i \pm \sin \beta_i \tan \alpha_i]; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (1)$$

123 where α_i is the angle between the vertical at the focal point and the line
 124 connecting the centre point of each mirror to the focal point. The sign
 125 \pm must be adopted according to the following criteria: $-$ for the left side,
 126 and $+$ for the right side. The angle α_i can be calculated as:

$$\alpha_i = \arctan \left[\frac{i \cdot (W + d)}{f + D/2} \right]; \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (2)$$

127 The length of the circumference illuminated on the absorber tube (L_{ai}) by
 128 the i -th mirror for $0 \leq i \leq 2n$, can be calculated as:

$$L_{ai} = \begin{cases} \frac{\pi D}{2} & \text{if } W_{ai} \cos \alpha_i > D \\ D \arcsin \left(\frac{W_{ai}}{D} \right) & \text{if } W_{ai} \cos \alpha_i \leq D \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

129 2.3. Parameters used in the longitudinal study

130 As shown in Barbon et al. (2016), the parameters used in the longitudinal
 131 study are as follows: angle between the mirror axis and the horizontal plane
 132 (β_M), angle between the absorber tube and the horizontal plane (β_a), zenithal
 133 solar angle (θ_z), mirror length (L_M), distance between the absorber and

134 the mirror (f), angle between the reflected beam and the zenith (μ), and
 135 angle between the incident ray and the normal plane to the mirror (θ_L).
 136 These parameters allow the calculation of the left illuminated length of the
 137 absorber (l_{abs}^l), the right illuminated length of the absorber (l_{abs}^r), and the
 138 total illuminated length of the single absorber tube (l_{abs}).

139 2.4. Mirror field area

140 The parameters that influence the installation of SSLFRs on building
 141 roofs are of two types: those intrinsic to the SSLFR and those relating to
 142 the roof. The potential number of SSLFRs to be installed on a roof strongly
 143 depends on these parameters. Fig. 1.b shows the area required for the
 144 installation of a SSLFR, that is, the mirror field area (A_{fw}), which is given
 145 by:

$$A_{fw} = L_M \cdot [2n(W + d) + W] \quad (4)$$

146

147 2.5. Power absorbed

148 Different equations are used in the literature to determine the power
 149 absorbed by the absorber tube of a LFR (see, for example, Morin et al.
 150 (2012), Elmaanaoui et al. (2014) and Cau et al. (2014)). We will use a
 151 version of these equations presented by Barbón et al. (2016b), that it is
 152 particularly suitable for the case of SSLFRs:

$$Q = \sum_{i=0}^{2 \cdot n} DNI \cdot \eta_{opt} \cdot IAF_i \cdot A_{effi} \quad (5)$$

153 where these parameters are:

- 154 (i) DNI is the direct normal irradiance.
- 155 (ii) η_{opt} is the total optical yield, which is calculated considering the reflec-
 156 tivity of the mirrors (ρ), the cleanliness factors of the mirror (CI_m) and of the
 157 glass covering the secondary absorber (CI_g), the transmissivity of this glass
 158 (τ), and the absorptivity of the material of which the absorber tube is made
 159 (α). Although some of these parameters, especially τ , should change with the
 160 angle of incidence (see Duffie et al. 2013), in this study they are considered
 161 constant for simplicity (see Binotti et al. (2014), Moghumi et al. (2015)).
 162 These values are: $\rho = 0.94$ (see Duffie et al. 2013); $CI_m = CI_g = 0.96$ (see
 163 Sharma et al. 2015); $\tau = 0.87$ if $\alpha_i \leq 20^\circ$, $\tau = 0.85$ if $20^\circ \leq \alpha_i \leq 30^\circ$ (see
 164 Theunissen et al. 1985).

165 (iii) IAF_i considers the variation in the optical performance of a SSLFR
 166 for varying ray incidence angles, by the i -th mirror:

$$IAF_i = \left[A^2 + B_i^2 + 2 \cdot A \cdot B_i \cdot \cos \widehat{AB_i} \right]^{1/2}; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (6)$$

167 where A (common to all the mirrors) and B_i (different for each mirror) are
 168 the components of the reflected radiation, and their values are given by:

$$A = \cos \gamma_S \cdot \cos \theta_L; \quad B_i = \frac{\cos \alpha_S \cdot \sin \gamma_S \cdot \cos \theta_i}{\sin \theta_t}; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (7)$$

169 Fig. 2 shows the components of the reflected radiation (A and B_i).

Fig. 2. Components of the reflected radiation.

170 (iv) A_{effi} is the effective area of the absorber tube by the i -th mirror
 171 that is actually illuminated, which is calculated considering the length of the
 172 circumference illuminated on the absorber tube by the i -th mirror (L_{ai}), and
 173 the total illuminated length of the absorber tube (l_{abs}):

$$A_{effi} = L_{ai} \cdot l_{abs}; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (8)$$

174 3. Parameters object of study

175 In this study, the mirrors and the absorber tube are not provided with
 176 longitudinal movement. We will study 4 different configurations for the rela-
 177 tive position between the field of primary mirrors, the absorber tube and the
 178 horizontal plane.

Table 1. Characteristics of each configuration.

	Mirrors	Absorber
Configuration	β_M ($^\circ$)	β_a ($^\circ$)
C ₁	0	0
C ₂	λ	0
C ₃	λ	λ
C ₄	0	$-\lambda$

179 Table 1 shows these 4 configurations. C₁ is the configuration used in large-
180 scale LFRs, where the mirrors and the absorber tube form an angle of 0° with
181 the horizontal plane. This configuration will be used as a basis for the sake
182 of comparison with the others. Configuration C₂, has an angle of inclination
183 of the mirrors equal to the latitude, with the absorber tube remaining in
184 the horizontal position. In configuration C₃, both mirrors and absorber tube
185 have an inclination equal to the latitude. In configuration C₄ the mirrors
186 form an angle of 0° with the horizontal plane and the absorber tube has
187 an inclination equal to minus the latitude. The configurations that imply
188 inclining the entire mirror row and/or inclining the entire absorber tube seem
189 to work only for SSLFRs, since it would be unrealistic to incline large-scale
190 LFRs.

191 The tilt angle is chosen equal to the site latitude, as in the so-called single
192 axis polar solar tracker, which sometimes add a correction as a function of the
193 declination. With this arrangement, the rotation axis of the mirror, oriented
194 in the N-S direction, is parallel to the Earth’s axis. Compared to two axes
195 systems, single axis systems are reported to reach yields of 96%.

196 3.1. Critical parameters

197 In large scale LFRs, the optimization of the longitudinal position and
198 length of the absorber tube is not considered. However, in a SSLFR this
199 longitudinal optimization is essential, that is, the longitudinal position and
200 length of the absorber tube are critical parameters for the study of a SSLFR.
201 The longitudinal optimization involves the calculation of the optimal values
202 of the total length, left length, and right length of the absorber tube (L_{abs} ,
203 L_{abs}^l , and L_{abs}^r respectively).

204 As can be seen in Barbón et al. (2016b), the longitudinal position and
205 length of the absorber tube are two critical parameters for the design of a

206 SSLFR. Using non-optimal values leads to decreases of up to 80% in the
 207 energy produced.

208 This comparative analysis uses the optimal values of L_{abs} , L_{abs}^l , and L_{abs}^r .
 209 In (Barbon 2016b) a new mathematical algorithm that allows the optimiza-
 210 tion of

211 the position and length of the absorber tube based on the longitudinal
 212 design is presented. The method is based on a geometrical algorithm that
 213 minimizes

214 the area between two curves, minimizing the end loss and reflected light
 215 loss, which are now taken into consideration. Table 2 summarizes these
 216 values for $f = 1.5$ (m) and $L_M = 2$ (m), in Almeria (Spain), with lati-
 217 tude $36^\circ 50' 07'' N$, longitude $02^\circ 24' 08'' W$ and Berlin (Germany), with latitude
 218 $52^\circ 31' 7'' N$, longitude $13^\circ 24' 37'' E$.

Table 2. Optimization of the length and position of the absorber tube.

Configuration	Almeria			Berlin		
	L_{abs}^l	L_{abs}^r	L_{abs}	L_{abs}^l	L_{abs}^r	L_{abs}
C ₁	-0.425	-2.425	2.00	-0.865	-2.865	2.00
C ₂	2.807	0.047	2.76	3.862	0.393	3.468
C ₃	2.029	0.029	2.00	2.190	0.190	2.00
C ₄	-0.300	-1.756	1.456	-0.581	-1.798	1.217

219 With the sign convention that we have adopted, lengths from the centre of
 220 the mirror to the left are considered positive, and those to the right, negative.

221 3.2. Parameters used in the comparative analysis

222 The following parameters remain constant in all the configurations:

- 223 (i) $n = 12$, considered optimal for the design of a SSLFR.
- 224 (ii) $D = 0.0486$ (m), considered appropriate in the manufacture of the
 225 prototype, since the absorber tube is manufactured from standardized carbon
 226 steel tubes (UNE EN 10255). This diameter is the standardized value that
 227 best conforms to the dimensions of the prototype that is being built.
- 228 (iii) L_{abs} , L_{abs}^l , and L_{abs}^r , see Table 2.
- 229 (iv) $d = 0.024$ (m), this value is used by Barbon et al. (2016), where
 230 the authors use a method inspired by what is known as ‘Mathur’s method’
 231 (Mathur et al. 1991 and 1991b), which calculates the appropriate value of the
 232 shift between adjacent mirrors such that shading and blocking of reflected

233 rays are avoided. Using this method, the effects of shading and blocking are
 234 avoided, for a transversal incidence angle between -22.5° and 22.5° . In any
 235 case, the numerical simulations, performed using MATLAB, also take into
 236 account the effects of shading and blocking, in those hours in which they
 237 exist.

238 The comparative analysis is performed changing parameter values around
 239 the following values, considered as basic dimensions (D_B):

240 (i) $f = 1.5$ (m), considered optimal for the design of a SSLFR and ob-
 241 tained by applying Mathur's method.

242 (ii) $L_M = 2$ (m), considered optimal for the design of a SSLFR and
 243 obtained by applying Mathur's method.

244 (iii) $W = 0.060$ (m), considered optimal for the design of a SSLFR.

245 Table 3 summarizes the parameter values selected for the analysis in each
 246 configuration. These values are expressed in percentage terms of the basic
 247 dimensions.

Table 3. Geometrical parameters of the selected configurations.

Parameters	% D_B				
	D_1	D_2	D_3	D_4	D_5
f	70	85	100	115	130
L_M	70	85	100	115	130
W	70	85	100	115	130

248 3.3. Evaluation of the shading of the absorber tube

249 Figure 3 shows the most the transversal shading of the absorber tube.
 250 The transversal shading of the absorber tube can be determined using the
 251 following equation:

$$S_t = \frac{D}{\cos \theta_t} \quad (9)$$

252 where S_t is the transversal shading of the absorber tube (m). According to
 253 Fig. 3 is met:

$$L_{ts} = \left(f + \frac{D}{2} \right) \cdot \tan \theta_t \quad (10)$$

254 where L_{ts} is the position of the transversal shading of the absorber tube (m).

$$L_i = i \cdot (W + d); \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (11)$$

255 where L_i is the position of i -th mirror ($0 \leq i \leq n$) (m). There is no
 256 transversal shading if:

$$\left(L_{ts} + \frac{S_t}{2}\right) - \left(L_i + \frac{W_{ai}}{2}\right) > S_t; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (12)$$

257 OR

$$\left(L_i + \frac{W_{ai}}{2}\right) - \left(L_{ts} + \frac{S_t}{2}\right) > W_{ai}; \quad 0 \leq i \leq 2n \quad (13)$$

Fig.3. Transversal shading of the absorber tube.

258 4. Results and discussion

259 Regardless of the application where the SSLFR will be used (domestic
 260 water heating or heating/cooling for buildings), the thermal behaviour is not
 261 the only concern. As SSLFRs are usually installed on building roofs, the
 262 mirror field area, given by the parameters M_{fw} and L_M , has to be carefully
 263 considered.

264 All the calculations are based on sub-hourly distribution of direct normal
 265 irradiance in a specific geographic location: Almeria (Spain), with latitude
 266 $36^{\circ}50'07''N$, longitude $02^{\circ}24'08''W$ and altitude 22 m. and Berlin (Germany),
 267 with latitude $52^{\circ}31'7''N$, longitude $13^{\circ}24'37''E$ and altitude 37 m. Derived
 268 database and system integrating data (PVGIS) have been used to estimate
 269 the solar irradiance. Numerical simulations were performed using the com-
 270 putational software package MATLAB. The program developed incorporates
 271 subroutines, discretized every 10 minutes, to calculate: DNI , mirror po-
 272 sition, IAF , L_{ai} , and l_{abs} . The program takes into account the effects of
 273 shading, blocking and end loss.

Tabla 4. Energy absorbed by the absorber tube (MWh)

	<i>January</i>		<i>February</i>		<i>March</i>		<i>April</i>	
	Alm	Ber	Alm	Ber	Alm	Ber	Alm	Ber
C1	0.39	0.11	0.47	0.19	0.74	0.33	0.81	0.51
C2	0.37	0.21	0.46	0.33	0.75	0.54	0.84	0.79
C3	0.38	0.21	0.47	0.32	0.73	0.46	0.77	0.60
C4	0.31	0.06	0.38	0.12	0.59	0.20	0.66	0.31
	<i>May</i>		<i>June</i>		<i>July</i>		<i>August</i>	
	Alm	Ber	Alm	Ber	Alm	Ber	Alm	Ber
C1	0.90	0.70	0.93	0.64	0.96	0.70	0.91	0.61
C2	0.97	1.08	1.05	1.00	1.06	1.09	0.96	0.94
C3	0.87	0.75	0.91	0.67	0.94	0.74	0.87	0.68
C4	0.77	0.43	0.81	0.39	0.83	0.43	0.76	0.37
	<i>September</i>		<i>October</i>		<i>November</i>		<i>December</i>	
	Alm	Ber	Alm	Ber	Alm	Ber	Alm	Ber
C1	0.73	0.40	0.59	0.26	0.41	0.13	0.36	0.08
C2	0.75	0.64	0.58	0.43	0.39	0.24	0.34	0.17
C3	0.71	0.51	0.58	0.40	0.40	0.24	0.35	0.17
C4	0.59	0.24	0.47	0.16	0.33	0.08	0.29	0.05

274

275 *4.1. Influence of the parameters on the energy absorbed by the absorber tube*

276 Table 4 shows the energy absorbed by the absorber tube per month,
 277 in each configuration, in Almeria (Alm) and Berlin (Ber), for the basic di-
 278 mensions. Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 shows, for each configuration, different cases
 279 have been considered, changing the value of the following parameters: mirror
 280 length (L_M), receiver height (f), and mirror width (W). The influence of
 281 these parameters is evaluated calculating, in percentage terms of the basic
 282 dimensions (see Table 3), the change in the monthly energy absorbed by the
 283 absorber tube.

284 **Variation of L_M**

285 In configuration C_1 , the influence of increasing L_M is almost nil in the
 286 winter months because the negative declination causes reflected rays in this
 287 extra length not to reach the absorber tube in almost no time of any day.
 288 The length and position of the absorber tube remain constant and they are
 289 optimized so that end losses are minimized throughout the year (Barbón
 290 2016b). In winter, the center of the illuminated zone is quite displaced (up
 291 to 3.5 m to the right from the center of the mirrors) and this motivates the
 292 previous effect. However, in summer with positive declination, the gain is up

293 to 10%, because now the center of the illuminated zone is less displaced (1m
 294 to the right from the center of the mirrors). All these data can be consulted
 295 in Fig. 8 (Barbón 2016b).

Fig. 4. Monthly energy as a function of the f , L_M and W in Almeria.

296 On the contrary, in configurations C_2 and C_3 , when the mirrors are in-
 297 clined an angle equal to the latitude, this effect is reversed. For example,
 298 referring to configuration C_3 , in summer the illuminated zone is displaced 1.5
 299 m to the left from the center of the mirrors, so that the gain is still around
 300 10%. But this gain rises to 25% in winter, because the displacement is much
 301 smaller (about half) and then those rays reflected by the extra part can reach
 302 the absorber tube. The reasoning is similar for the case of a decrease in the
 303 parameter.

304 In configuration C_4 , the behavior is similar to configuration C_1 , since the
 305 illuminated zone follows an analogous pattern. In addition, due to the small
 306 optimum size of the absorber tube ($L_{abs} = 1.217\text{ m}$), the variation of L_M has
 307 no influence.

308 In Almeria, in configurations C_1 and C_4 the influence of the mirror length
 309 is greater in summer. In contrast, in configurations C_2 and C_3 the influence
 310 is greater in winter.

Fig. 5. Monthly energy as a function of the f , L_M and W in Berlin.

311 Variation of f

312 When analyzing the increase of f we must take into account that there
 313 are two factors that will influence the reflection of the rays and therefore
 314 the energy absorbed. First, the effect of the position and length of the
 315 absorber tube is similar to that already mentioned above when analyzing the
 316 influence of L_M , and for this reason the reader can observe the same general
 317 tendency with respect to the summer and winter months. Secondly, we must
 318 also consider the cosine factor. It is known that this factor, present in IAF_i
 319 calculation (eq 6), has a great influence on the energy produced. Moreover, in
 320 the equinoxes the declination is null, resulting, at noon, in rays perpendicular
 321 to the mirrors when their angle is equal to the latitude. Therefore, the
 322 results in configurations C_2 and C_3 , are as expected: as the days of the

323 equinox approach, the cosine factor improves and hence the local maximums
324 in absorbed energy on the general trend marked by the influence of the
325 position of the absorber tube. This effect does not appear in configuration
326 C_1 because here the surfaces remain horizontal.

327 In Almeria, configuration C_4 follows a pattern similar to configuration
328 C_1 . In Berlin, due to latitude, the variation is constant throughout the year.

329 In Almeria, in configurations C_2 and C_3 the influence of the receiver height
330 is greater in equinoxes, while in configurations C_1 and C_4 the influence is
331 greater in summer.

332 **Variation of W**

333 The influence of W is constant throughout the year, since, from the
334 transversal point of view, the solar movement throughout the year does not
335 change. In addition, the increase in W has less influence than its decrease.
336 The reason for this behavior is found in the formulas used to calculate Q . An
337 analysis of this equations shows that IAF_i (eq 6) includes the parameter A ,
338 common to all the mirrors, and the parameter B_i which is different for each
339 mirror. Moreover, A_{effi} includes L_{ai} , the length of the circumference illumi-
340 nated on the absorber tube by the i -th mirror, where W_{ai} (eq 1) depends on
341 each mirror.

342 The increase in W causes an increase in A_{effi} (eq (8)). But the mirrors
343 are then further away from the center of the SSLFR, which results in higher
344 θ_i values that make IAF_i smaller and, therefore, the gain of Q is reduced.
345 However, with a decrease in W , the influence of θ_i is lower and the main
346 effect is the decrease in A_{effi} .

347 *4.2. Influence of the parameters on the shading of the absorber tube*

348 In this section we will study the effect of receiver height (f) and mirror
349 width (W) on the shading of the absorber tube. Mirror length (L_M) does
350 not have any influence on shading. The following parameters have been used
351 for this calculation: Almeria (latitude $36^{\circ}50'07''N$, longitude $02^{\circ}24'08''W$),
352 21 June, configuration C_1 .

Fig. 6. Shading on the mirrors with variation of receiver height f .

Fig. 7. Shading on the mirrors with variation of mirror width W .

353 Figure 6 shows the results of the transversal shading on the mirrors as
 354 a function of the solar time and the receiver height (f). As a simplification
 355 we show only the shading on 3 mirrors. For example, for $f = 100\%$, the
 356 central mirror reaches 96.87% of transversal shading at 12:00, while at 12:11
 357 the transversal shading is 0%. Moreover, the duration of the shading on the
 358 mirrors increases with a decrease in f .

359 Figure 7 shows the results of the transversal shading on the mirrors as a
 360 function of the solar time and the mirror width (W). The duration of the
 361 shading on the mirrors increases with W .

362 In order to evaluate the total shading on the mirrors, we define a shading
 363 index for each day of the year. First we calculate, for each mirror, the shading
 364 in percentage terms as a function of time. Then we integrate this function for
 365 each mirror and, finally, the shading index is calculated as the ratio between
 366 the shaded area over a day and the mirror area.

Fig. 8. Shading index with variation of receiver height f .

Fig. 9. Shading index with variation of mirror width W .

367 Figure 8 shows the value of the shading index as a function of the receiver
 368 height (f). As can be seen, the shading index increases with a decrease in

369 f . Figure 9 shows the value of the shading index as a function of the mirror
 370 width (W). As can be seen, the shading index increases with W . Moreover,
 371 the receiver height has a somewhat stronger influence on shading than the
 372 mirror width.

373 4.3. Sensitivity analysis of the parameters

374 In order to evaluate the importance of the parameters f , L_M and W , a
 375 sensitivity analysis was carried out. This analysis evaluates, for each configura-
 376 tion, the influence of one parameter at a time while keeping the others fixed
 377 (one-at-a-time method), by using normalized sensitivity coefficients (NSCs)
 378 (see Siddiqui et al. 2013). The NSCs for a particular independent vari-
 379 able can be calculated from the partial derivative of the dependent variable
 380 with respect to the independent variable (see Hamby et al. 1994), using the
 381 equation:

$$NSC_i = \frac{\partial Y}{\partial X_i} \cdot \left(\frac{X_i}{Y} \right) \quad (14)$$

382 where $\frac{\partial Y}{\partial X}$ is the partial derivative of the dependent variable, Y , with respect
 383 to the independent variable X_i . $\left(\frac{X_i}{Y} \right)$ is introduced to normalize the coeffi-
 384 cient by removing the effects of units. For each configuration, the maximum
 385 power output is considered to be the function Y and X_i are the parameters
 386 f , L_M and W . The results of the sensitivity analysis are shown in Table 5.

387 As shown in Table 5, the parameter with the highest NSC is W , which is
 388 also practically constant throughout the year, for the four configurations. As
 389 regards L_M , its greatest influence takes place in the months of reduced solar
 390 irradiance, except for configuration C_1 and C_4 where the NSC values are lower.
 391 Finally, the NSC values of f are around 0.2 – 0.3 in the four configurations.
 392 It should be noted that f is a parameter that does not modify one of the key
 393 parameters of design: the mirror field width (M_{fw}). Nevertheless, f has to
 394 be taken into account as regards the shading effects between close SSLFRs.

Table 5. Normalized sensitivity analysis results in Almeria.

Month	f				L_M				W			
	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄
1	0,106	0,271	0,267	0.142	0	0,717	0,738	0	1,053	1,053	1,053	1.054
2	0,105	0,355	0,348	0.163	0	0,661	0,667	0	1,050	1,046	1,048	1.050
3	0,135	0,366	0,325	0.191	0,022	0,579	0,549	0.033	1,047	1,037	1,041	1.046
4	0,243	0,244	0,248	0.229	0,155	0,379	0,408	0.120	1,043	1,029	1,035	1.042
5	0,275	0,206	0,213	0.261	0,245	0,295	0,320	0.180	1,041	1,025	1,031	1.039
6	0,274	0,203	0,211	0.269	0,271	0,272	0,299	0.214	1,039	1,023	1,029	1.037
7	0,275	0,201	0,208	0.267	0,261	0,280	0,306	0.200	1,040	1,024	1,030	1.038
8	0,268	0,212	0,229	0.244	0,204	0,332	0,362	0.142	1,042	1,027	1,034	1.040
9	0,180	0,312	0,287	0.207	0,070	0,487	0,485	0.064	1,044	1,033	1,039	1.044
10	0,108	0,382	0,359	0.174	0	0,645	0,624	0.008	1,048	1,043	1,045	1.048
11	0,106	0,302	0,297	0.149	0	0,693	0,712	0	1,052	1,051	1,052	1.053
12	0,106	0,242	0,239	0.136	0	0,740	0,763	0	1,055	1,055	1,055	1.055

395 5. Conclusions and future perspectives

396 This paper addresses the thermal behaviour of a SSLFR, analysing the
 397 influence of design parameters in the energy absorbed by the absorber tube.

398 The variation of the design parameters receiver height, mirror length,
 399 and mirror width that describe the transversal and longitudinal design of
 400 a SSLFR were analyzed, considering the optimal values of the length and
 401 longitudinal position of the absorber tube. We have compared the results
 402 obtained for different values of the parameters used.

403 The simulations carried out in this paper provide a detailed analysis of
 404 how design parameters affect the performance of a SSLFR, which is essential
 405 in order to design an efficient SSLFR. The contributions of this study can
 406 be particularly used in the design of SSLFRs to be installed on roofs of
 407 buildings, in which the available surface is the most limiting factor. The
 408 mathematical model allows to evaluate the influence of design parameters in
 409 the area needed to install the reflector.

410 Numerical simulations show that receiver height, mirror length, and mir-
 411 ror width, have a strong influence on the energy absorbed. Among the anal-
 412 ysed cases, a decrease of 30% in the mirror width leads to a maximum de-
 413 crease in the energy absorbed of almost 59%, an increase of 30% in the

414 receiver height leads to a maximum increase in the energy absorbed of al-
415 most 8%, and an increase of 30% in the mirror length leads to a maximum
416 increase in the energy absorbed of almost 24%.

417 We have also studied the influence of the receiver height and the mirror
418 width on the shading of the absorber tube. We have found that the shading
419 index increases as the receiver height decreases and the mirror width in-
420 creases. Moreover, the receiver height has a greater impact on shading than
421 the mirror width.

422 The mirror field area has to be carefully considered, specially if several
423 SSLFRs are to be installed close from one another in a building roof. This
424 parameter depends mainly on the mirror width and the mirror length. The
425 receiver height does not directly affect the mirror field area, however, the
426 shading effects between close SSLFRs need to be analysed.

427 With regard to possible future works, we are studying the three-movement
428 SSLFR. This design, currently in the process of industrial patent application
429 in Spain, allows the longitudinal movement of both the primary mirror field
430 and the absorber tube in the N-S direction. Secondly, we are studying the
431 relationship between the roof-related parameters (available roof area, roof
432 form, and roof orientation) and the aspect ratio (AR) of the mirror field
433 area:

$$AR = \frac{2n(W + d) + W}{L_M} \quad (15)$$

434 Finally, we believe that in order to make better use of the area available on the
435 roofs of urban buildings, it would be very helpful to perform a mathematical
436 optimization of the distribution of SSLFRs.

437 **Acknowledgments**

438 We wish to thank M. F. Fanjul, director of the vocational training school
439 (CIFP-Mantenimiento y Servicios a la Producción) in La Felguera, Asturias,
440 Spain, and the teachers L. Rodríguez and F. Salguero for their work on the
441 (on-going) building of the prototype for the design presented in this paper.

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